

How the Prime Number Theorem likely implies not just the simple Goldbach Conjecture but a much stronger version

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Abstract

In a previous paper (see "*Why the Goldbach conjecture is likely true*", *Ismael Afaf and Mikhael Afaf, February 2023*), Mikhael and I computed the exact number of Goldbach prime pairs ($NumExactGPPs(2N)$) per even number, for even numbers up to 80,000, and showed that the number of pairs increases, on average, as $\frac{N}{\ln N}$. Based on these results we suggested that the Goldbach conjecture was not only likely true, but that the number of Goldbach prime pairs increased, on average, with increasing even numbers (with some oscillations). In this paper, I start with the *Prime Number Theorem (PNT)*, and estimate the probability of the number of Goldbach prime pairs (which I now call $NumProbabilisticGPPsFromPMT(2N)$) per even number as a direct consequence of the *PNT*. I then show that exact computed Goldbach prime pair numbers ($NumExactGPPs(2N)$) follow a trend around the estimated probability of the number of Goldbach prime pairs, per even number, $NumProbabilisticGPPsFromPNT(2N)$, deduced from the *Prime Number Theorem*. By taking running averages, and running averages of running averages, in small averaging windows of 5 points, I show that the curves for $NumProbabilisticGPPsFromPMT(2N)$ and $NumExactGPPs(2N)$ are virtually indistinguishable for even integers up to 160,000 (higher numbers computed upto 350,000 but not displayed here). This result implies that (a) the average number of Goldbach Prime Pairs per even number is a direct consequence of the *PNT* (b) that the *PNT* explains the exact computed numbers on average and (c) that not only is the Goldbach Conjecture likely true, but a much stronger conjecture that the number of GPPs grows proportional to $\frac{N}{\ln N}$ is most likely true, not just from computed numbers and an observed trend, but from probabilistic arguments deduced from the *PNT*.

I want to thank my dad, Nasir Afaf, for proof-reading my paper, suggesting major stylistic changes and letting me use his favourite Lenovo ThinkPad laptop for performing the computations in this paper.

1 Introduction and the Method

Shortly after Mikhael and I submitted our first paper, one morning at a school dropoff in February 2023, it occurred to me that if I knew the probability of any odd number being prime, then I could compute the probability of pairs of odd numbers both being prime, and use that to get an estimate for the number of Goldbach prime pairs for any even number $2N$. For example, for the even number 100, if I knew the probabilities of the pairs (3, 97), (5, 95), ... all the way up to (49, 51), being both prime, I could sum up these probabilities to get an estimate for the number of pairs of Goldbach primes that sum to 100. I thought since prime numbers are fairly randomly distributed I could get the joint probability of a pair such as (3, 97) both being prime by simply multiplying the probability of 3 being prime by the probability of 97 being prime. In other words $p(3 \cap 97) = p(3) * p(97)$, where $p(i \cap j)$ is the probability of both i and j being prime and $p(i)$ and $p(j)$ are the probabilities of i and j being primes individually.

I soon forgot this thought, easy come, easy go, and got busy with other activities including iGCSE revision. I also did not know how to compute the probabilities of any odd number being prime. It is clear that odd numbers that are non-prime have $p(\text{non-prime odd}) = 0$ and odd numbers that are prime have $p(\text{prime odd}) = 1$, so it wasn't even clear that my idea made any sense. It was just a quick observation, soon forgotten, not very useful at all.

But then during iGCSE prep, around mid May 2023, the idea suddenly occurred to me that the total number of primes up to a number N is equal to the sum of the probabilities of all odd numbers being prime or not.

$$\pi(N) = \sum_{i=1}^N p(i) \tag{1}$$

And then I remembered the $\frac{N}{\ln N}$ function I had looked up on Wikipedia, which seemed to show the trend observed in our previous paper. I looked it up and realised this is called the *Prime Number Theorem (PNT)* which has different approximations for $\pi(N)$ in Equation 1. These approximations are smooth curves as opposed to $\pi(N)$ which is jumpy. I then decided to also write an equation for these approximations in terms of Equation 1.

$$A(N) = \sum_{i=1}^N p_a(i) \tag{2}$$

Where $A(N)$ is a smooth approximation to the jumpy $\pi(N)$ and $p_a(i)$ are the probabilities of i being prime in such a way that $A(N)$ approximates $\pi(N)$.

Note it was clear to me that $p_a(\text{non-prime odd}) > 0$ and $p_a(\text{prime odd}) < 1$ because $A(N)$ is smooth but somehow the total sum still approximates $\pi(N)$. So in my head I call these $p_a(i)$ fake probabilities, individually wrong, but their sums giving a very good approximation for $\pi(N)$

From here, I then realised I can calculate these fake probabilities $p_a(i)$ by:

$$p_a(N) = A(N) - A(N - 1) \quad (3)$$

In fact since apart from 2 no even numbers are prime, equation 3 is better rewritten as:

$$p_a(2M + 1) = A(2M + 1) - A(2M - 1) \quad (4)$$

Where the arguments represent odd numbers.

From here I could then calculate the fake probability of any pairs of odd numbers being prime.

$$p_a(i \cap j) = p_a(i) * p_a(j) \quad (5)$$

Where $i = 2N + 1$ and $j = 2M + 1$.

Note, since $A(N)$ is a smooth function, the fake joint probability satisfies:

$$0 < p_a(i \cap j) < 1 \quad (6)$$

While the real probabilities $p(i \cap j)$ is strictly either 0 or 1.

Now my expectation was that by using Equation 5 for a number $2N$ by focussing on the mid, say for even, N choosing my odd pairs as $N - \text{Offset}$ and $N + \text{Offset}$ over all offsets giving all odd pairs $(3, 2N - 3)$, $(5, 2N - 5)$, $(7, 2N - 7)$, etc all the way to $(N - 1, N + 1)$. I could compute the total number of estimated for an even N :

For an even number $2N$ when N is even we can write:

$$G_P(2N) = \sum_{M=\frac{N}{2}}^{N-1} p_a(2M + 1) \cdot p_a(2N - 2M - 1) \quad (7)$$

For an even number $2N$ when N is odd we can write:

$$G_P(2N) = \sum_{M=\frac{N}{2}}^{N-1} p_a(2M+1) \cdot p_a(2N-2M-1) \quad (8)$$

where $G_P(2N)$ is the total number of PNT deduced Goldbach Prime Pairs for the even number $2N$ using the PNT approximation $A(N)$

After looking at the Wiki page, I decided to use the approximation:

$$A(x) = Li(x) = \int_2^x \frac{dt}{\ln t} = li(x) - li(2) \quad (9)$$

According to Wikipedia this could be approximated as a series which is what I used in the next section of the results:

$$A(x) = Li(x) = \frac{x}{\ln x} + \frac{x}{x^2} + \frac{2x}{\ln x^3} + \dots \quad (10)$$

2 Results

I then wrote up Python Code, this time with some help from ChatGPT because I was impatient to see results, and printed these out to text files, which I also opened in Excel for smaller numbers (Excel is very cumbersome for graphing large number of data points).

The graphical results are presented in 2 different graphs:

In the first graph below, I have plotted the number of exact GPP pairs, a running average over 5 exact GPP pairs, and the PNT deduced number of GPP pairs. As can be seen, the oscillations in the exact GPP pairs does not us see the PNT deduced number of GPP pairs:

Figure 1:

To get around this issue of graphical display, I then used another running average, over 5 points each, of the original running average over 5 points of the exact GPP pairs. Once I did this, the graphs from the running average of running average of exact GPP pairs just collapsed on the PNT deduced GPP pairs. It is difficult to see the differences:

Figure 2:

Because in graph 2 it was difficult to see the differences, here I have taken a screenshot from Excel of the last few even numbers before 160,000 comparing the double smoothed (running average of running average) exact GPP pairs versus the PNT deduced GPP pairs to give an idea of the closeness of the match:

EvenNumber	Probabalistic Estimate From PNT	RunningAverOfRunningAverage5NumbersExactGCPairs
159,948	1,331.79	1,331.76
159,950	1,331.71	1,331.75
159,952	1,331.82	1,331.78
159,954	1,331.74	1,331.78
159,956	1,331.85	1,331.81
159,958	1,331.77	1,331.81
159,960	1,331.87	1,331.84
159,962	1,331.80	1,331.83
159,964	1,331.90	1,331.86
159,966	1,331.82	1,331.86
159,968	1,331.93	1,331.89
159,970	1,331.85	1,331.89
159,972	1,331.96	1,331.92
159,974	1,331.88	1,331.91
159,976	1,331.98	1,331.95
159,978	1,331.90	1,331.94
159,980	1,332.01	1,331.97
159,982	1,331.93	1,331.97
159,984	1,332.04	1,332.00
159,986	1,331.96	1,332.00
159,988	1,332.07	1,332.03
159,990	1,331.99	1,332.02
159,992	1,332.09	1,332.06
159,994	1,332.01	1,332.05
159,996	1,332.12	1,332.08
159,998	1,332.04	1,332.08
160,000	1,332.15	1,332.11

Figure 3:

3 Discussion

The above results show that if the Prime Number Theorem is true, then it can be used to compute an average number of Goldbach Prime Pairs for any even number $2N$. Further these numbers show a very close match with smoothed versions of the actual computed exact Goldbach Prime Pairs. This suggests a few possibilities: (a) the Goldbach conjecture is likely true (b) a much stronger conjecture than the Goldbach Conjecture is true, that on average, with some oscillations, **the number of Goldbach Prime Pairs is not only > 0 for each even number, but follow a $N/\ln N$ type of trend** (c) that it maybe that the Goldbach conjecture fails for some finite number of even numbers $2N$ but is otherwise true and (d) that the Goldbach conjecture is at least asymptotically true just like the Prime Number Theorem.

I myself think that the Goldbach conjecture is too weak and much stronger statements can be made, such as suggested above.

If I have time I want to think about the growth of oscillations in the Goldbach Prime Pairs, which also seem to roughly follow a width proportional to $N/\ln(N)$. Maybe I will get an idea at some point and explain why this grows in the same manner.

4 References

1. *"Why The Goldbach Conjecture is likely true"*, Ismael Afaf and Mikhael Afaf, February 2023
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Prime_number_theorem